

Glycyrrhizic acid and its salts as antioxidant; A computational investigation

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Abstract : In this work, the density functional theory method were used to investigate the ground state energies, spin density, atomic charge distribution, HOMO-LUMO gap, O-H bond dissociation enthalpies (BDEs) and ionization potential (IP) of the glycyrrhizic acid (GL) and its monolithium, monosodium, monopotassium and monoammonium salts in the gas phase. The results show that there is a clear correlation between O-H BDE and the spin density and the atomic charges. The more delocalized spin density in the radicals and the higher atomic charges of remaining O-atoms after H-removal is equivalent to the lower BDE and higher antioxidant character in H-atom transfer mechanism. The obtained values for the IP indicate that the lowest IP having the lowest HOMO-LUMO gap (ΔE). Nevertheless, the trend of the IP cannot be interpreted only on the basis of the ΔE . However; the inclusion of Li, Na, K and NH_3 improved the stability of GL molecule and all of the radicals. We believe that the obtained results may be helpful in the field of biological antioxidant study.

Keywords : Glycyrrhizic acid, bond dissociation enthalpy, computational chemistry, antioxidant character, ionization potential.

Introduction

Glycyrrhizic acid (glycyrrhizin, GL), is the triterpene glycoside from *Glycyrrhiza glabra* root. Historically, the dried rhizome and root of this plant were employed medicinally by the Egyptian, Chinese, Greek, Indian, and Roman civilizations as an expectorant and carminative¹. Wide range of biological activity and interesting curative properties are known for GL and its derivatives².

The anti-inflammatory activity is combined with anti-ulcer action caused by the increase of capability of the synthesis of nucleic acids in the stomach mucosa. The anti-allergic action of GL is associated with its activity as an antagonist of acetyl choline, histamine and other biogenic amines stimulating allergic reactions^{3,4}.

The antidotal activity of GL is most probably determined by the presence of two units of glucuronic acid in its structure. GL and its salts can antagonize lethal doses of strychnine, nicotine, caffeine, histamine and another poison and recommended for the application as intoxicants. GL prevents rat hepatocytes injury under direct influence of such toxins as allyl formiate and linolic acid^{3,5}.

GL is one of the first natural glycosides inhibiting the human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1)⁶. Monotherapy with GL started early in asymptomatic HIV-1 carrier patients have been effective to maintain their state for more than 11 years without induction of drug resistance⁷.

Many considerations have been focus on the GL salts, in connection to the development of methods for preparation of GL from raw materials and to the search of medicinal forms. A series of non-toxic mono and trisubstituted salts of GL were obtained with the purpose of research of pharmacological properties^{8,9}. GL and its monoammonium salt inhibits the growth of DNA and RNA viruses *in vitro*¹⁰, also monoammonium salt of GL used as an anti-inflammatory and anti-allergic remedy for the medical care of bronchial asthma, eczemas and other diseases¹¹. Monosodium and mixed potassium-dilithium salts showed the high anti-ulcer activity and were more potent as compared to GL and cimetidinum⁸. Monoammonium and monosodium salts of GL inhibited HIV-1 and HIV-2 reproduction in the MT-4 cells cul-

ture¹². In addition, glycyrrhizic acid and its derivatives exhibited antioxidant activity¹³⁻¹⁸. Antioxidants are of great interest because of their role in important biological and industrial processes. Two main mechanisms are proposed to explain the protective role for antioxidants. One is the H-atom transfer, in which a free radical R[•] removes a hydrogen atom from the antioxidant and the other one is a one-electron transfer mechanism, where the antioxidant can give an electron to the radical¹⁹⁻²². The first mechanism is governed by the O-H bond dissociation enthalpy (BDE), direct hydrogen atom transfer (HAT)²³ while the second one is governed by the ionization potential and by the reactivity of the ROH[•] cation, single electron transfer (SET) mechanism²⁴.

Low values of BDE and ionization potential (IP) correspond to a good antioxidant capacity¹⁹. The mechanisms of hydrogen/electron transfer in radical reactions were explored in many experimental and computational studies²⁵⁻³⁵. SET and HAT mechanisms usually occur together in all samples, with the balance determined by antioxidant structure and pH²⁸.

A lot of attention was given to GL and its salts with the purpose of research of pharmacological properties. The most widely reported side-effects of glycyrrhizin use are hypertension and edema (water retention). The evaluation of the biological effects of GL showed that glycyrrhizinic acid itself is hardly absorbed from the gastro-intestinal tract. Before absorption, GL is hydrolysed to give glycyrrhetic acid, which is the ultimate biologically active metabolite. Glycyrrhetic acid is an inhibitor of the enzyme 11-beta-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase-2 and via this inhibition it causes a cortisol-dependent increased sodium and water retention and an increased potassium excretion. As a result they should be used with caution in people. Evaluation of toxicological information for glycyrrhizinic acid showed that the upper limit for regular ingestion of 100 mg/day provides a sufficient level of protection for the majority of the population³⁶.

Investigations of the chemical properties of bioactive natural substances have become an important direction in the modern medicinal chemistry. The specific medicinal

and biological activity and the lack of theoretical details in term of chemical nature of glycyrrhizic acid and its various salts encourage us to exploit the chemical calculation tools for determination of molecular and thermodynamic properties.

In the present work, density functional theory (DFT) study was performed to investigate the glycyrrhizic acid and its mono substituted lithium, sodium, potassium and ammonium salts. The computation of various molecular descriptors such as total energies, spin density, Mulliken atomic charge distribution, HOMO-LUMO energy gap, O-H bond dissociation enthalpies and ionization potential of the glycyrrhizic acid and its mono Li, Na, K and NH₃ salts in the gas phase were carried out and evaluated. The results are compared regarding the ground state energy and the relation of OH-BDE and IP to the spin density distribution, Mulliken atomic charges and the HOMO-LUMO gap.

Methodology :

All of the calculations reported in this study were performed with DMol3 (Accelrys Inc.)^{37,38}. Molecular geometries were optimized without constraints at the local DFT functional with Perdew and Wang's gradient-corrected correlation functional, PWC^{39,40} employing the medium settings and Double Numerical plus d-functions (DND) basis set. DND basis set exploits one atomic orbital (AO) for each occupied atomic orbital plus a second set of valence AOs with a polarization d-function on all non-hydrogen atoms. The unrestricted open-shell approach was used for computations of radical species. Harmonic vibrational frequencies were computed at the same level of theory for both parent and radical molecules, with the aim to characterize them as minima and saddle points and to estimate zero point energy and thermodynamic properties. The bond dissociation enthalpies for hemolytic O-H bond cleavage in the gas phase at 298.15 K, were calculated as the enthalpy of the radical resulting from the hydrogen atom abstraction plus the enthalpy of hydrogen atom, -0.49765 Hartree⁴¹, and minus the energy of the parent molecules. The IP in the gas phase were calculated as the energy difference between a radical cation and the respective parent molecule. Electron density

analysis carried out to better characterize the electronic volumetric properties of the orbitals with the 0.25 Å grid interval value.

Results and discussion

The optimized geometry of GL molecule has been shown in Fig. 1. For the sake of simplicity, this study is restricted to a single conformation for each molecule, which is the global minimum configuration. The total energies, O-H BDEs, spin density and Mulliken atomic charge distribution, IP and HOMO-LUMO gap of the all species in the gas phase are calculated.

Energy data :

Computed total energy values, E_{tot} , of the GL molecule and its monolithium, monosodium, monopotassium and monoammonium salts were found to be about -2819, -2826, -2980, -3417, -2874, respectively (all in a.u.). As seen from the total energies, presence of Li, Na, K and NH_3 ions make the molecule more stable. The inclusion of the potassium effect shifts the energy of GL around 598 a.u. down.

The calculated gas-phase total energies of the optimized geometry radicals after H-atom being abstracted in each demonstrated site (1 to 5 in Fig. 1) of the glycyrrhizic acid and its announced salts are reported in Table 1. In order that, the single hydrogen atom at the denoted sites (1 to 5) has been removed and the geometry of these radicals has been optimized. As observed in Table 1, the addition of Li, Na, K and NH_3 ion improved the stability of all of the radicals. K salt radicals are more stable than other species. However, the total energies of different site in each row are roughly same.

BDE, spin density and Mulliken atomic charge :

The cleavage of H atom from the carboxyl group can cause a consecutive C-C bond break, resulting in CO_2 dissociation (decarboxylation), while oxygen-centered radical species is transformed into a carbon-centered one. In addition, in the aqueous phase the carboxyl group is deprotonated, so there is no O-H bond to be broken. Therefore, in order to estimate the contribution of the HAT mechanism, the BDE values (kcal/mol) at 298.15 K for the five radicals formed by H-abstraction on each OH

Fig. 1. The optimized structure of glycyrrhizic acid (in mono substituted salts, Li, Na, K and NH_3 have been replaced with H in exhibited position. Sites No. 1 to 5 in A and B ring display the OH groups in which hydrogen atom was abstracted from a molecule).

Table 1. The calculated gas phase total energies (a.u.) of the optimized geometry radicals after H-atom being abstracted in each demonstrated site (1 to 5) of the glycyrrhizic acid (GL) and its announced salts

	1	2	3	4	5
GL	2818.23	2818.22	2818.22	2818.22	2818.21
Mono Li-GL	2825.16	2825.13	2825.14	2825.14	2825.13
Mono Na-GL	2979.27	2979.23	2979.23	2979.24	2979.23
Mono K-GL	3415.99	3416.00	3415.98	3415.99	3415.98
Mono ammonium GL	2873.10	2873.10	2873.09	2873.09	2873.09

site (1 to 5) of the glycyrrhizic acid and its preferred salts are calculated and reported in Table 2. It is known that, in DFT method, which does not supply enthalpies in a direct manner, the total enthalpies of the species (H) at temperature T are usually assessed from this expression²⁶:

$$H = E_0 + ZPE + \Delta H_{\text{vibration}} + \Delta H_{\text{rotation}} + \Delta H_{\text{translation}} + RT \quad (1)$$

where E_0 is the calculated total electronic energy, ZPE stands for zero-point energy, $\Delta H_{\text{translation}}$, $\Delta H_{\text{rotation}}$ and $\Delta H_{\text{vibration}}$ are the translational, rotational and vibrational contributions to the enthalpy. RT represents PV-work term and is added to convert the energy to enthalpy. Table 2, shows the calculated BDE values (kcal/mol) at 298.15 K for the five radicals formed by H-abstraction on each OH site (1 to 5) of the glycyrrhizic acid and its preferred salts in the gas phase. As shown in Table 2, the O-H BDEs in the A-ring are relatively lower than B-ring, indicating the higher capacity of 1 and 2 -OH groups to transfer H atoms. For GL and its monolithium and monosodium salts, the lowest BDEs are those of site No. 1 OH groups (around 97, 96 and 85 (kcal/mol), respectively). For monopotassium and monoammonium salt species, the BDEs of site No. 2 are lower compared to other OH groups. However, the presence of the Li, Na, K and NH_3 ions leads to an increase of the BDE in the B-ring, which may suggest a corresponding lower antioxidant capacity.

The spin density is an important parameter to depict the stability of free radicals, since the energy of a free radical can be efficiently decreased if the unpaired electrons are highly delocalized through the system after hydrogen abstraction⁴²⁻⁴⁴. Therefore, we have decided to analyze the spin density on the various radicals, in order to rationalize the differences in reactivity of the OH sites and consequently the differences in BDE.

Fig. 2, shows that the calculated spin densities in some radicals formed by H-ejection from the GL and its mentioned salts. The more delocalized the spin density, the easier the radical is formed and the lower the BDE. For the OH group of a, b and c of Fig. 2, it is delocalized on related ring and carboxylic acid while in the d, e and f the spin density is strongly localized on the O atom from the original radicalization site.

Delocalization of spin density (Fig. 2a, b, c), indicating efficient stabilization of the formed radicals, on the contrary, localized spin density on the O atom (Fig. 2d, e, f), indicating that those sites weakly participate in H-abstraction mechanism. This is in agreement with the low and high BDE (Table 2), respectively. The low BDEs are attributed to the high capacity for radical delocalization in radicals while the high BDEs are ascribed to intensely localized spin density on the O atom from where the H atom is removed.

In order to investigate the antioxidant character, Mulliken atomic charge is computed as a molecular descriptor. Table 3 summarizes the computed values for Mulliken atomic charges on the remaining O-atoms after H-removal of the glycyrrhizic acid and its selected salts. The obtained data shows that the highest atomic charges of remaining O atom in GL and its monolithium, monosodium, monopotassium and monoammonium salts are -0.487 (site No. 1), -0.561 (site No. 1), -0.558 (site No. 1), -0.561 (site No. 2), -0.432 (site No. 2), respectively.

It is interesting to make a general comparison of BDEs (Table 2) and Mulliken atomic charges (Table 3). Analysis of the data from these two tables show that for each compound, the highest atomic charge and the lowest BDE takes place in same situation radicals. The high value of the atomic charge confirms that the considered site is

Table 2. Calculated BDE values (kcal/mol) at 298 K for the five radicals formed by H-abstraction on each OH site (1 to 5) of the glycyrrhizic acid (GL) and its preferred salts in the gas phase

	1-OH	2-OH	3-OH	4-OH	5-OH
GL	97.786	109.893	105.325	103.384	107.676
Mono Li-GL	96.035	109.450	109.453	108.999	111.353
Mono Na-GL	85.549	108.576	107.999	106.629	109.677
Mono K-GL	104.795	95.377	111.820	105.420	107.960
Mono ammonium GL	105.805	101.835	112.668	111.457	110.642

Fig. 2. Spin density distribution in the radicals formed by H-ejection from the (a) GL (site No. 1); (b) monoLi-GL salt (site No. 1); (c) monoNa-GL salt (site No. 1); (d) monoNa-GL salt (site No. 4); (e) monoK-GL salt (site No. 5); (f) monoammonium GL salt (site No. 3).

Table 3. Mulliken atomic charges of remaining O-atoms (site No. 1 to 5) after H-removal of the glycyrrhizic acid and its selected salts.

	1	2	3	4	5
GL	-0.487	-0.408	-0.339	-0.412	-0.415
Mono Li-GL	-0.561	-0.400	-0.317	-0.322	-0.420
Mono Na-GL	-0.558	-0.397	-0.317	-0.393	-0.420
Mono K-GL	-0.336	-0.561	-0.402	-0.355	-0.355
Mono ammonium GL	-0.348	-0.432	-0.390	-0.335	-0.359

more likely to give H-atom, a fact that is equivalent to the antioxidant character in HAT mechanism.

Ionization potential and HOMO-LUMO gap :

In order to determine the efficiency of SET mechanism, we calculated the IP as the energy required to remove an electron from the ground state of the molecule. Table 4 shows the calculated IP, the energy of the highest occupied molecular orbital, HOMO, the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital, LUMO, and the HOMO-LUMO gap, ΔE , which is evaluated by the $\Delta E = E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$.

The ionization potential is the significant energetic factor for scavenging activity evaluation. The lower the IP, the easier is the electron abstraction. As shown in Table 4, the presence of the Li, Na, K and NH_3 ions

Table 4. The calculated ionization potential (IP), the energy of HOMO, LUMO and the HOMO-LUMO gap, ΔE , in gas phase

	IP (kcal/mol)	HOMO (eV)	LUMO (eV)	ΔE
GL	156.889	-5.123	-2.364	2.759
Mono Li-GL	137.938	-5.148	-2.448	2.700
Mono Na-GL	153.976	-5.135	-2.308	2.827
Mono K-GL	147.859	-4.937	-2.131	2.806
Mono ammonium GL	148.631	-5.130	-2.371	2.759

appears to be decreasing the IP values and weakly influencing the HOMO and LUMO energies. The lowest IP is obtained for monoLi-GL salt having the lowest HOMO, LUMO and ΔE , although the trend of HOMO, LUMO energy and ΔE was different from the manner of obtained IP in the gas phase. The GL and monoNa-GL molecules

seem to be the less active systems in the framework of an electron transfer mechanism. Unfortunately, no experimental data is available in literature for these molecules, therefore no comparison between our computed and experimental values is possible.

Conclusion

In summary, some molecular descriptors and thermodynamic parameters, total energies, spin density, Mulliken atomic charge distribution, HOMO-LUMO gap, BDE and IP, were computed for glycyrrhizic acid and its monolithium, monosodium, monopotassium and monoammonium salts. The results show that the presence of Li, Na, K and NH₃ ions improved the stability of GL molecule and all of the radicals. The spin density and the Mulliken atomic charges are important parameters to characterize the stability of free radicals. As clearly seen from our results, the most delocalized the spin density in the radicals and the highest atomic charge of O-atom in each radical lead to the lowest BDE, which may propose a corresponding highest antioxidant capacity. The lowest IP and the lowest HOMO, LUMO gap is obtained for monoLi-GL salt. Nevertheless, differences in the IP cannot be explained only on the basis of the HOMO, LUMO energy gap.

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